

Strengthening Sustainability Education for Future Food Systems

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

The transition towards sustainable food systems is critical for addressing global challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss and food insecurity. Recognising the role of education in preparing graduates to address interconnected sustainability challenges, this study examined how nutrition and agri-food educators understand, teach, and integrate food sustainability concepts into curricula. The study explored the knowledge, perceptions, and teaching practices of educators participating in the Erasmus+ Train to Sustain project across Ireland, Italy, Poland, and Slovenia. By identifying strengths, gaps, and barriers in sustainability education, the study sought to inform curriculum reform and support more comprehensive and interdisciplinary approaches to sustainability teaching.

Research Findings

The findings demonstrated strong recognition among nutrition and agri-food educators of the importance of embedding sustainability within education. Educators showed strongest awareness of environmental and social sustainability issues, particularly food waste reduction, ethical consumption, local food systems, and resource management. Experiential learning approaches were commonly used to engage learners with sustainability concepts. However, the study identified more limited understanding of economic sustainability, cultural dimensions, and whole food systems thinking. Participants also highlighted the need for additional professional development, practical teaching resources, and interdisciplinary curriculum approaches to strengthen sustainability education and better prepare graduates.

Policy Implications

The findings highlight important policy implications for sustainability education within the agri-food and nutrition sectors. Greater integration of food sustainability across curricula may be supported through interdisciplinary and systems-based approaches aligned with UNESCO sustainability education frameworks and relevant Sustainable Development Goals. The study also demonstrates the need for continuous professional development to improve educators' understanding of economic and cultural dimensions of sustainability. Investment in accessible teaching resources, digital learning tools, and experiential learning opportunities is needed to support curriculum delivery. Monitoring and evaluation frameworks are also needed to assess how sustainability education develops student competencies.

Industry Recommendations

The findings highlight opportunities for industry stakeholders to support curriculum development through partnerships that provide real-world learning opportunities, including farm visits, case studies, placements, and guest expert contributions. Greater engagement with educators could also improve understanding of economic sustainability, food system resilience, fair trade, and sustainable supply chains. The findings further suggest a need for industry-led training and knowledge exchange on emerging practices such as circular agriculture, resource-efficient technologies, and sustainable production methods to help equip graduates with the practical sustainability skills and systems-thinking required to meet evolving workforce and food system challenges.

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Further Reading:

McDonagh, M., Moloney, R.,
Moran, A. & Ryan, L. (2025)
Exploring Nutrition and Agri-Food
Educators' Knowledge of Food
Sustainability: Insights Addressing
Sustainability Education.
Sustainability, 17(20), 9119. DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su17209119>

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**Sustainable Development Goal
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